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Herbert Bruderer

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Books

Meilensteine der Rechentechnik, De Gruyter, 2. Auflage 2018

Meilensteine der Rechentechnik, De Gruyter, 3. Auflage 2020

Milestones in Analog and Digital Computing, Springer, 3rd edition 2020

Meilensteine der Rechentechnik, De Gruyter, 1. Auflage 2015

Konrad Zuse und die Schweiz, 1. Auflage 2012

References

- Bruderer, Herbert [2012]: Konrad Zuse und die Schweiz, De Gruyter Oldenbourg, Berlin/Boston, 1. Auflage 2012, 250 Seiten, <https://doi.org/10.1524/9783486716658>
- Bruderer, Herbert [2015]: Meilensteine der Rechentechnik, De Gruyter Oldenbourg, Berlin/Boston, 1. Auflage 2015, 850 Seiten, <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110375619>
- Bruderer, Herbert [2018a]: Meilensteine der Rechentechnik, De Gruyter Oldenbourg, Berlin/Boston, 2. Auflage 2018, Band 1, 751 Seiten, <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110520705>
- Bruderer, Herbert [2018b]: Meilensteine der Rechentechnik, De Gruyter Oldenbourg, Berlin/Boston, 2. Auflage 2018, Band 2, 849 Seiten, <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110602616>
- Bruderer, Herbert [2020a]: Meilensteine der Rechentechnik, De Gruyter Oldenbourg, Berlin/Boston, 3. Auflage 2020, Band 1, 970 Seiten, 577 Abbildungen, 114 Tabellen, <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110669664>
- Bruderer, Herbert [2020b]: Meilensteine der Rechentechnik, De Gruyter Oldenbourg, Berlin/Boston, 3. Auflage 2020, Band 2, 1055 Seiten, 138 Abbildungen, 37 Tabellen, <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110669671>
- Bruderer, Herbert [2020c]: Milestones in Analog and Digital Computing, Springer Nature Switzerland AG, Cham, 3rd edition 2020, 2 volumes, 2113 pages, 715 illustrations, 151 tables, translated from the German by John McMinn, <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-40974-6>

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